

Automated Ontology Term Mapping for Enhanced Research Data Annotation

A Framework for Interoperability and Flexibility

Hannah Dörpholz¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9436-3109>,
Kathryn Dumschott¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8510-6810>,
Marcel Tschöpe³ <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3925-6778>,
Dirk von Suchodoletz³ <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0921-8041>
and Angela Kranz¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8000-0400>

¹ Institute of Bio- and Geosciences (IBG-4: Bioinformatics), CEPLAS, BIOSC, Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, Wilhelm Johnen Straße, Jülich, Germany

² Computational Systems Biology, RPTU University of Kaiserslautern, Kaiserslautern, Germany

³ Computer Center, University of Freiburg, Freiburg im Breisgau, Germany

⁴ Heinrich-Heine University Düsseldorf, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Institute for Biological Data Science, CEPLAS, Düsseldorf, Germany

*Correspondence: Hannah Dörpholz, h.doerpholz@fz-juelich.de

Abstract

As research data management becomes more integrated into the day-to-day workflows of scientists, it is crucial to ensure (meta)data annotation is meaningful and aimed towards making data more accessible and reproducible. Here, ontologies play a particularly important role by providing standardized, machine-readable vocabulary for data annotation. Within the German National Research Data Consortium (NFDI) DataPLANT [1], the framework that has been developed to aid researchers in their data annotation has been refined and improved, with a focus on with ontologies relevant for plant sciences.

A key component of this framework is SwateDB, a database comprised of ontology terms from established ontologies we identified to be relevant for plant sciences [2]. They are made available to researchers through the annotation software Swate [3], which operates on familiar tabular files. To overcome gaps in ontologies, where specific, relevant terminology is missing, the DataPLANT Biology Ontology (DPBO) was developed [4]. DPBO serves as a broker ontology to facilitate the addition of new terms not present in other external ontologies, avoiding time-consuming submissions to established ontologies. By leveraging GitHub issues, users can request new terms to be incorporated into DPBO, as well as additions of entire new ontologies to SwateDB. Furthermore, an automated GitHub workflow for the generation of PURLs for each newly added term was established, providing persistence to the ontology.

Since many relevant ontologies were identified on OBO-Foundry [5], the initial infrastructure focused on consuming ontologies in OBO-format [6] due to its easy readability for cura-

tors. To expand and make our annotation framework applicable in other research areas, where OBO-format is not common, a connection to the TIB terminology service was established, which enables the consumption of OWL files [7]. Furthermore, specific collections composed of relevant ontologies in different research areas can be set, enabling researchers to adjust the annotation terms they will be provided with.

To improve interoperability, additional efforts have been made towards mapping DPBO to existing ontologies, making use of python and sssom (simple standard for sharing ontology mappings). The mapping relies on similarity identification between term names and semantic context of the definitions. This will ensure ontology orthogonality and encourage term reuse instead of duplication.

To further improve DPBO and the plant ontology landscape, existing terms currently are reviewed and suggested to external ontologies in a lengthy manual process, with the identification of suitable ontologies for each term being the bottleneck. To streamline the process, we aim to integrate automated term mappings. This principle will then be applied to improving existing research metadata annotations where free-text was used instead of ontology terms, increasing the overall value and FAIRness of the data.

In conclusion, the presented framework provides a robust and flexible solution for ontology-based research data annotation, while addressing the needs of researchers from across different domains. Expanding the developed tools towards additional ontology formats allows for a more comprehensive consumption of relevant ontologies within different research areas, further improving research data annotations.

Keywords: DataPLANT, ontology, mapping

Resources

The material and resources (e.g. data, model, codes, documentation, videos) which underly, support or are closely related to your contribution deposited on a repository, please include a title, the respective DOI(s) and brief description. E.g.

- DPBO, a link to the DataPLANT Biology Ontology on GitHub: https://github.com/nfdi4plants/nfdi4plants_ontology
- DataPLANT TS4TIB collection: <https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies?and=false&page=1&sortedBy=title&size=10&collection=DataPLANT>
- DataPLANT TS4TIB search results list widget to search the DataPLANT collection on the TS4TIB server: https://ts4nfdi.github.io/terminology-service-suite/comp/latest/?path=/story/react_search-searchresultslistwidget--tib-data-plant
- PURL Administration where DPBO PURLs are set up: https://purl.archive.org/domain/nfdi4plants_ontology_dpbo
- Swate, the DataPLANT tool for data annotation: <https://swate-alpha.nfdi4plants.org/>

Author contributions

Hannah Dörpholz	Data curation, Formal analysis, Software, Writing – original draft
Angela Kranz	Project administration, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Supervision
Stella Eggels	Data curation, Formal analysis
Kevin Frey	Software
Timo Mühlhaus	Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision
Björn Usadel	Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing
Dirk von Suchodoletz	Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision
Kathryn Dumschott	Data curation, Methodology
Marcel Tschöpe	Methodology, Software

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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